

Acid Dissociation Constants of Morin in Ethanol-water Mixture

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pK_1 and pK_2 for the first and the second acid dissociation constants of morin in 0.05M sodium perchlorate solution containing 38% by volume of ethanol have been determined by pH measurements to be 5.30 ± 0.05 and 8.74 ± 0.07 respectively at $30^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$. Increase in the concentration of ethanol from 19 to 77% by volume results in the increase of pK_1 and pK_2 by 0.47 and 0.85 units respectively.

The acidic character of morin (3,5,7,2',4'-pentahydroxyflavone) is exhibited by its solubility in alkali. This is further supported by the fact that the hydrogen of the hydroxyl group in 3 or 5 position of morin can be replaced by an equivalent of metal to form chelate complexes. The acid dissociation constants of morin have not yet been determined. The present communication describes determination of the first and the second acid dissociation constants of morin in ethanol-water mixture by pH measurements. The first and the second stages of ionisation of morin, $(HO)_3M$, can be represented as

The first (K_1) and the second (K_2) acid dissociation constants are given by

$$K_1 = \frac{[H^+][HO_4MO^-]}{[(HO)_3M]} \quad \dots (1)$$

and

$$K_2 = \frac{[H^+][HO_3MO_2^{2-}]}{[(HO)_4MO^-]} \quad \dots (2)$$

$$\bar{n}_H = \frac{2[H^+]^2 + K_1[H^+]}{[H^+]^2 + K_1[H^+] + K_1K_2} \quad \dots (3)$$

provided that the ionic strength of the solution is kept constant. Terms in square brackets represent concentrations and

$$\bar{n}_H = \frac{2[(HO)_3M] + [(HO)_4MO^-]}{[(HO)_3M]_T}$$

where $[(HO)_3M]_T$ = total concentration of morin used. When $[(HO)_3MO_2^{2-}]$ is negligible, compared to $[(HO)_3M]$ and $[(HO)_4MO^-]$, the relation,

$$pK_1 = pH + \log \frac{\bar{n}_H - 1}{2 - \bar{n}_H} \quad \dots (4)$$

is obtained. Similarly when $[(HO)_2M]$ is negligible, compared to $[(HO)_4MO^-]$ and $[(HO)_3MO_2^{2-}]$, pK_2 is given by

$$pK_2 = pH + \log \frac{\bar{n}_H}{1 - \bar{n}_H} \quad \dots (5)$$

Thus measuring pH and determining $\bar{n}_H$ under proper experimental condition, pK_1 and pK_2 can be calculated with the help of equations (4) and (5).

Irving and Rossotti¹ have discussed the method of determination of n_H , utilising the Bjerrum-Calvin pH -titration technique. It is as follows. The pH -meter is calibrated with aqueous buffer and the reading R is plotted as a function of volume V of alkali used to titrate the aqueous ethanol solution containing (i) strong acid and (ii) strong acid and morin. At a given value of R , the concentrations of H^+ are constant provided that the activity coefficients are controlled. Then

$$\bar{n}_H = 2 - \frac{(V_2 - V_1)N}{V_0[(HO)_2M]_T} \quad \dots (6)$$

V_0 = total volume of the solution. V_1 and V_2 are the volumes of alkali of strength N molar added to a strong acid solution and to strong acid and morin solution respectively at a given value of R . V_1 and V_2 are usually negligible compared to V_0 .

The pH in ethanol-water mixture was measured by Van Uitert and Haas² who found the following relation to hold good:

$$R = pH - \log U \quad \dots (7)$$

where U is a correction term and is a function of mole fraction of ethanol and ionic strength. The pH -meter reading can therefore be converted to pH by means of equation (7), if the correction term U is determined for the appropriate solvent, salt medium, and temperature. The correction term U can be evaluated by measuring pH of the same concentration of hydrochloric or nitric acid in water and in ethanol-water mixture. Combining equations (4), (5), and (7) the following relations are obtained:

$$pK_1 = R + \log U + \log \frac{\bar{n}_H - 1}{2 - \bar{n}_H} \quad \text{or} \quad pK_1' = R + \log \frac{\bar{n}_H - 1}{2 - \bar{n}_H} \quad \dots (8)$$

$$pK_2 = R + \log U + \log \frac{\bar{n}_H}{1 - \bar{n}_H} \quad \text{or} \quad pK_2' = R + \log \frac{\bar{n}_H}{1 - \bar{n}_H} \quad \dots (9)$$

$K_1U = K_1'$, = practical first acid dissociation constant.

$K_2U = K_2'$, = practical second acid dissociation constant.

Therefore, from the knowledge of $\bar{n}_H$ and pH -meter readings, pK_1' and pK_2' can be determined with the help of equations (8) and (9).

EXPERIMENTAL

All the reagents used were of A. R. quality. The melting point of A. R. quality morin, available in the market, was found to be 290°. In one set of experiments morin was further purified as follows.

1. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 2904.

2. Van Uitert et al., *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 451.

Morin was Soxhleted for 5 hours with absolute ethanol, the extract was diluted with an equal volume of water, and the precipitated morin was filtered. The product was dissolved in ethanol and reprecipitated with water. The morin was dissolved in 90% acetic acid (30ml) and heated to boiling. HBr (conc., 20 ml) was added to it and the morin hydrobromide was filtered, washed with a small amount of 90% acetic acid, transferred to a beaker, and boiled with water to decompose the hydrobromide. The product was filtered, washed with water, and dried at 120°. The yield was only 40%, m.p. 290° (decomp.).

Ethanol, redistilled in an all-glass apparatus, was used. Aqueous solutions were made in doubly distilled water (free from traces of Cu) prepared by distilling distilled water from alkaline permanganate solution in an all-glass apparatus. Carbonate-free, A.R. grade NaOH was dissolved in doubly distilled water and strength of the alkali solution was determined by titration with a standard succinic acid solution, using phenolphthalein as an indicator.

Sodium perchlorate solution was prepared either by dissolving pure sodium perchlorate in water or by neutralising perchloric acid with NaOH. The strength of sodium perchlorate solution was checked by reducing perchlorate to chloride and determining the chloride as silver chloride.

FIG. 1. pH meter reading R as a function of the drops of alkali added to solutions containing (a) 0.00438 M - HNO_3 and (b) 0.00438 M - HNO_3 +0.004 M morin.

Measurements of pH were taken with an L & N pH meter, using glass electrode, model No. CAP 7666 and a saturated calomel electrode. pH meter was calibrated with aqueous phthalate buffer of pH 4.0 and checked with a borate buffer solution of pH 9.1. The procedure for a typical titration is given below.

A beaker of 250 ml was used as a titration vessel. In one beaker 2 ml of 0.2193 M - HNO_3 +10ml of 0.5 M - $NaClO_4$ +40ml of 0.01 M morin solution in EtOH+48 ml of water were added. In the second beaker 2ml of 0.2193 M - HNO_3 +10ml of 0.5 M - $NaClO_4$ +40ml of EtOH+48 ml of water were added. The titration vessels, each covered with card board provided with four holes, were kept in a thermostat, maintained at $30^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$. Glass and

calomel electrodes were introduced through two holes. The third hole was used for stirrer. The tip of the burette provided with a jet just closed the fourth hole. The solutions were titrated with 0.3253*M*-NaOH (42 drops=1ml). Similar titrations were performed with other concentrations of morin and in presence of different amounts of EtOH. The results of titrations of morin in ethanol-water mixture are summarised in Tables I to IV.

TABLE I

Determination of practical acid dissociation constant of morin.

Morin = 0.004*M*. %EtOH by volume =38. HNO₃=0.004386*M*, NaOH =0.3253*M*. NaClO₄=0.05*M*. Temp. of the thermostat=30.0°±0.1°. Total volume=100 ml.

pH.	$\bar{\alpha}_n$.	$pK'_{1.}$	pH.	$\bar{\alpha}_n$.	$pK'_{1.}$
4.60	1.874	5.44	8.40	0.800	9.00
5.00	1.729	5.43	8.60	0.703	8.97
5.20	1.652	5.47	8.80	0.586	8.95
5.40	1.558	5.50	9.00	0.528	9.05
5.50	1.500	5.50 (graph)	9.05	0.500	9.05 (graph)
5.60	1.457	5.52	9.10	0.490	9.08
Av. 5.48±0.05			Av. 9.01±0.07		

Solutions containing partially neutralised nitric acid and a requisite quantity of sodium perchlorate were prepared in water and in ethanol-water mixture. pH meter readings of such solutions were recorded.

TABLE II

Conditions same as in Table I

*Conc. of morin.	*Conc. of alkali.	Average $pK'_{1.}$	Average $pK'_{1.}$
0.001	0.2145	5.55	8.92
0.004	0.3726	5.50	8.89
0.008	0.7460	5.45	8.95

*In g. moles/litre.

TABLE III

Determination of correction term log U.

Conditions same as in Table I

*Conc. of HNO ₃ .	*Conc. of NaOH.	pH (aq. soln.).	pH meter readings of soln. With % EtOH.	Log U.	Mean log U.
0.01	0.001183	2.12	2.22	-0.10	
	0.002366	2.20	2.30	-0.10	
	0.005965	2.50	2.60	-0.10	
0.003	0.0009786	2.60	2.8	-0.20	-0.20.0
		2.80	3.0	-0.20	
		3.00	3.2	-0.20	
0.002193	0.0006756	2.91	3.13	-0.22	-0.20.0
		3.17	3.35	-0.18	
		3.29	3.49	-0.20	
0.004386	0.000549	2.45	2.70	-0.25	-0.253
		2.50	2.76	-0.26	
		2.70	2.95	-0.25	
0.002193	0.0002138	2.70	3.00	-0.30	-0.300
		2.78	3.08	-0.30	
		2.82	3.12	-0.30	

*In g. moles/litre.

TABLE IV

Effect of ethanol conc. on acid dissociation constants of morin.

Conc. of morin=0.001M. Na perchlorate=0.05M. Temp.=30°±0.1°

%EtOH(by vol.).	pK'_1 .	$pK_1=(pK'_1+\log U)$.	pK_2 .	$pK_2=(pK'_2+\log U)$.
19.0	5.38	5.28	8.60	8.50
38.0	5.50	5.30	8.94	8.74
48.0	5.65	5.45	9.15	8.95
58.0	5.75	5.50	9.45	9.20
77.0	6.05	5.75	9.65	9.35

FIG. 2. $\bar{n}_H$ as a function of pH meter reading R .

DISCUSSION

Given pH-meter reading, R , the volumes of alkali used in the titration of strong acid (nitric acid) and strong acid plus morin have been determined from the titration curves, a representative of which is shown in Fig. 1. $\bar{n}_H$ is then calculated with the help of equation 6.

Fig. 2 represents the plot of $\bar{n}_H$ against the *pH*-meter readings. pK_1 ' and pK_2 ' which can be directly obtained from Fig. 2, are given by the *pH*-meter readings corresponding to $\bar{n}_H$ values 1.5 and 0.5.

From Tables I and II it is seen that the values for the practical acid dissociation constants K_1 ' and K_2 ' are independent of concentrations of morin and alkali used. The mean values for the term $\log U$ at different ethanol concentrations are shown in the last column of Table III. The variation of pK_1 and pK_2 with the concentration of ethanol in the solvent mixture suggests that the acid dissociation constant of morin decreases with increase in the %EtOH in the mixture. This is in agreement with the expectation that the ionisation of the acid should decrease with decrease in the dielectric constant of the solvent, as observed with other acids.

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